

PRIVATIZATION EFFECTS ON PERFORMANCE IN THE STATE-OWNED ENTERPRISES IN JORDAN

YOUSEF ABUORABI

Al-Ahliyya Amman University, Email: y.abuorabi@ammanu.edu.jo

KHALEEL AL-DAOUD

Al-Ahliyya Amman University, Email: k.aldaoud@ammanu.edu.jo

ABSTRACT

Privatization is the act of reducing the role of government or increasing the role of the private institutions of society in satisfying people's needs; it means relying more on the private sector and less on government. The Jordanian government adopted a privatization program in 1996 to enhance the efficiency and productivity of government owned companies. The principal objective of this study is to examine the effects of the privatization program on enhancing the performance of state-owned enterprises in Jordan. Therefore, we try to draw some highlights on the trend of recent literature reviews in the area. This may provide some guidelines for the research to proceed with the examination of the Privatization practices and their impact on the performance.

Keywords: Privatization, Performance, government, Jordan

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades and due to the global competition linked with the changes in the global market during the 1980s, the market shifted to internationalisation (Börjesson, & Dalberg, 2021). Governments switch to privatisation programs because they expected it would increase performance efficiency and improve the economic situation (Rahbar, Sargolzaei, Ahmadi & Ahmadi, 2012). Privatisation from the government's viewpoint enhances public companies' performance, and solves the social, economic and political issues that result from the poor role of the government in managing and monitoring their state-owned enterprises (SOEs) (Darwazeh & Dabaghia, 2018).

Governments believe that the private sector is outperforming the public sector due to the nature of the activities, procedures, optimal uses of resources and the goals they set (Seppala, Hukka & Katko, 2001). It is becoming quite hard to find a country that has not adopted a privatisation program or at least included it in their policy agenda (Kikeri & Nellis, 2004).

Privatisation is defined as the process of transferring the ownership of SOEs by selling the benefits or assets to the private sector (Kikeri & Nellis, 2004). Rahbar et al. (2012) stated that privatisation occurred when the government tries to allocate some or all of its SOEs, and transfers the ownership to the private sector. Savas (2000) defined privatisation as the transfer, through sale, of enterprise ownership in whole or in part to private hands.

Privatisation is a transfer of control and/or ownership of business and industry from the public realm to the private (Mansfield & Pollins, 2009). In 1961 the German government sold the

majority of Volkswagen stocks by issuing public shares which known later as the first privatisation transaction (Kouser, Azid & Ali, 2012). The program was founded for the first time in the United Kingdom under the Thatcher government in 1980, when the government felt disappointed with the weak indicators for the SOEs' performance and shifted to a privatisation program (Carter, 2013; Kouser et al., 2012.).

After the United Kingdom adopted its privatisation program, many countries followed and adopted privatisation programs like Denmark, Chile, Malaysia and Singapore. These countries believed in the program's ability to enhance company performance (Kouser et al., 2012). Countries like Sweden, Jamaica, Holland, Spain, France, Austria, and the United States have adopted the program by issuing public shares during the period 1986-1987.

Reports indicate that more than 2000 SOEs have been privatised since 1980 in more than 80 developing countries and more than 6800 companies worldwide. After 1987, the program spread very fast worldwide, especially in developing countries like Brazil, South America, Mexico, Africa, Bangladesh, and South Asia by issuing public shares or selling to another company (Kikeri & Nellis, 2004).

Since its proclamation, Jordan adopted the free market economy system where the private sector played the main role in the economy activities. During the seventies and eighties, the economic situation in Jordan has been classified as a mix economic, with provisions of grip from the government to some of the vital facilities such as education, health, transportation, communication, water and electricity. The poor role of government in managing these facilities, linked with the noticeable absence of the private sector increased the claims to review the ownership and management for these facilities (Giraldo, 2021). Many factors led to the dominance of the public sector in the country's economic activities, such as the increasing demand to develop the economic infrastructure, the need to address economic and social problems, and private sector reluctance to engage in capital intensive projects.

The public sector dominance over various activities resulted in severe economic structural imbalances and declining in the productivity levels and economic competence. This contributed to the fiscal deficit aggravation in the public sector and induced a high increase in the outstanding public debt with the debt service burden, as well the deficit in the balance of payments. The previously mentioned factors led to the economic crisis in the late eighties, and resulted in foreign reserves depletion, devaluation of the Jordanian dinar and deterioration in the standard of living.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND THE EMPIRICAL GAP

The importance of privatisation is indisputable. Many studies have highlighted the effect of privatisation on enhancing the performance of government companies in developed countries, while developing countries require need more studies. Following a lead from the developed countries and since the early 1980s, many developing countries had implemented a privatisation program. As a result, the ownership of a vast number of state-owned enterprises had been transferred to the private sector.

The performance of state-owned enterprises must be at a satisfactory level for both citizens and investors, and the monitoring and controlling process of these SOEs must be performed in a very efficiently way to ensure the productivity and profitability of these companies and reduce the accumulated losses. In order to create the conditions for public-private partnerships in infrastructure, the Jordanian government over the past ten years has introduced social protection systems and reform subsidies. The government clarifying the steps towards enhancing the company's performance promote an investment climate and ease of doing business.

Furthermore, the Syria and Iraq crises linked with adverse regional developments, remain the largest recent shocks affecting Jordan, as reflected in disrupted trade routes, the large refugee influx, and lower tourism inflows. The huge number of Syrian refugees entering the country has had a strong impact on the country's social fabric, security and economy. The real GDP growth in 2015 was 2.4%, which reflects an unexpected deceleration in the first quarter of the year, while real GDP growth is forecasted at 3% in 2016, reflecting additional investment projects in the medium term (Central Bank of Jordan, 2015).

As recently reported by the Jordanian Central Bank, the SOEs in Jordan are suffering from wasting resources, low productivity, low profitability and high indebtedness, linked with increasing pressure on the state treasury, which incentivises these companies to cover up their successive losses.

The alternatives are either keeping the ownership of these companies under government supervision or transferring it to the private sector, and both options are a crucial issue with regard to the economic situation. Growth-enhancing plans and sound economic policies are strongly needed to reduce the country's vulnerability to external shocks.

Furthermore, a Royal Letter of instructions urged the government to encourage the private sector to assume its leading role in economic development throughout the sectors, including health and education. As well, the government was inspired by the royal letter to set out a gamut of macro and microeconomic objectives that it aims to achieve through privatisation.

Facilitating conditions for the foreign investment and enhancing competitiveness leads to deliver the growth needed to generate profit, reduce the government debt and fight poverty. It is worth noting that some studies in Jordan studied individual cases of privatisation (Nahleh, 2002) but studies that investigate the effects of privatisation on improving SOEs performance are scarce. Therefore, this study attempts to assess the effect of changes in company ownership (privatisation) on enhancing performance in Jordanian SOEs.

The augmentation of public sector role on infrastructure projects including telecommunications, energy, transport, water, education, health and social care. Despite the partnership with the private sector in development of large and small production projects such as cement, potash and some projects in services and financial sectors, the government kept the role of encompassed the control over market mechanism, control pricing system and protect national production.

In 1990, political fallouts of the Gulf War were imposed new challenges on the Jordanian economy consisted mainly of stopping the Gulf countries to give periodic aid to Jordan, a large number of workers left gulf countries and back to Jordan, and the difficulties faced Jordan by receiving those workers and their families. While in the post-crisis, it is clear that the first year of the reform program has succeeded to some extent in restoring macroeconomic stability. Decline in public spending by 20% and increased local revenues by more than 7%, and the budget deficit has fallen by aid from 23% in 1988 to 5% in 1994 and the debt fell to 70% of national output.

On the other hand, some procedures were taken by the Jordanian government in the same stage, in order to control the inflation within acceptable limits; the inflation indicator was 25% in 1989 and reached 4% in 1994. With the beginning of 1993 the volume of private investment began to decline gradually to reach the level it was before the reform program, which led to a slowdown in economic growth and low rates in the value of local revenues during the second half of the nineties. In 1996, the economic agenda of the Jordanian government was contained privatisation policy as an essential ingredient in order to achieve the goals of the program already mentioned in previous chapters.

A review of the economic and living conditions that prompted successive Jordanian governments since the beginning of the last century to embrace privatisation as economic option, confirm that the options were very limited and it was necessary to go for privatisation at the end of the eighties synchronizing with the period of global trend of privatisation, mainly in European countries. Moreover, the economic crisis showed clearly the weakness of the Jordanian economic structure.

Jordan has witnessed from the middle of the last century, establishment of a number of companies in the private sector, but the weakness of the elements of the private sector in that period, in addition to political events required intervention by the government to own and manage these companies, and some of these companies were privatised in the mid-nineties by the Jordanian government.

During the monopoly period between the companies in the market, there was a negative impact on the consumer as a result of high prices of materials, yet the effect became positive after the field open for the entry of new companies into the market. Some companies got clear and significant improvement in financial indicators after the privatisation process, mainly due to the rise in the world price of raw material. The financial performance of some privatised companies showed obvious improvements. In industry sector, the improvement was due mainly to the strength of monopolistic of some companies like Cement Company over nine years, in addition to the significant increase in world prices for the raw materials of potash and phosphate. This reflected positively on the revenue the treasury through taxes and fees.

In the transport field, the global economic impacts have had the opposite effect on some companies in terms of the increase in fuel prices and intense competition with some of the companies in the Arabian Gulf countries. While the Duty Free Company has achieved a good level of profitability and had a good profit this effect in reducing the size of the Royal Jordanian

indebtedness, which was draining the public treasury in the past. In the telecom field, the main transaction was the restructuring and liberalization process by converting the Jordanian telecommunications company from monopolistic company income-generating to the treasury by the expense of the price to high quality service provider.

The figure 1 below shows the percent of what the JIC was held in the public shareholding companies.

Figure 1: Participation of the Jordan Investment Corporation in Public Shareholding Companies

Source: (World Bank, 1995, p.15)

Generally, Jordanian state-owned infrastructure companies and the public shareholder companies, were suffering from acute deficits, and had sustained losses which are at the expense of shareholder and taxpayers. In addition, the majority of these companies were overstaffed and constrained by civil service norms in hiring and firing, as well, there were invariably experienced government interference in pricing their products, furthermore, they were having a weak system of incentive and control, inadequate accounting system as well as an absence of monitoring system (Parker, (2004).

Results showed that profitability average in these companies, which the government control a high percent of its share, is lower than the companies which the government just control less than 15% of its shares (world Bank, 1995). Gokgur and Christen (2009) documented that according to the public claims, which appeal the government to reduce the total debt and improve the performance of state-owned enterprises in Jordan; Jordanian government found that there is a desperate need to resort privatisation program.

Figure 2 below illustrates the stages occurred before the country decides to implement privatisation, as a tool to solve the economic and poor performance problems.

Figure 2: Privatisation Reasons (Executive Privatisation Commission, 2014).

As a country seeking to follow globalization, and be in the same position with other regions, Jordanian government started a privatisation program and applies it in many Jordanian companies, in order to achieve the improvement and meet the previous demands which called to reduce the debt and increase the efficiency of the state-owned enterprises and in many fields as other countries have done.

The real translation of this approach to take a practical character appeared in 1985, as well, in 1989 when the government announced about a proposed strategy to start privatisation program, which was contain two main axes, the first one is to curtail the role of government in business

activities through sell the assets to the private sector, the second was to Increase the size of private independent investment by increasing the flexibility of the laws and regulations in the work environment of the private sector (Rumman & Bader, 2004). Furthermore, in 1994 and in order to allow and facilitate the entrance for the private investor, then to support and encourage the competition between different sectors, also to stop the monopoly policy, the government in Jordan started restructuring the governmental infrastructure companies (Gokgur & Christen, 2009).

The government's goal of this approach was to achieve economic and social development and equitable distribution of gains, on the other hand it should be noted in this regard that the expanding role of the public sector has been concentrated mainly in infrastructure projects such as telecommunications, energy, transportation, water, education, health and social welfare. However, it also included the participation with the private sector in the establishment of some large capital projects such as cement, potash and phosphate projects, and to a lesser extent in many companies in the industrial and service sectors and finance.

This expansion of the role of the state also includes control of market mechanisms and the price system, at the same time the protection of domestic production by various means. As a result of this expansion in the role of the public sector deep structural imbalances in the economic structure and the low level of productivity and economic efficiency significantly. This contributed to the worsening fiscal deficit in the public sector, the general budget and the budgets of independent institutions, which led to a significant rise in the stock of public debt and the burden of his service, high balance of payments deficit, which led to an economic crisis in the late eighties, was the depletion of reserves foreign currency and hence the deterioration of the exchange rate of the Jordanian dinar and declining living standards.

To meet these challenges, Jordan has taken it upon itself to implement national programs of economic reform aimed to restore fiscal and monetary stability, and the creation of a structural correction to provide a suitable environment for the resumption of the process of growth rates acceptable and sustainable. Despite the tangible successes on some levels of cash stability and build an appropriate level of reserves and some areas of structural adjustment, especially in the legislative side, but that achieving all the objectives of these programs requires more effort and the trend towards the privatisation program.

Warner, Aldag, & Kim, (2021) studied the managers' opinions about implementing the privatisation program, and to suggest the optimal style of this implementation. The study used a questionnaire to know the department managers opinions of the Jordanian electric company, the study documented that there are difficulties facing the implementation such as the bureaucracy in the procedures as well the low efficient productivity. Thiab (1999) assured that the management in the Jordanian private hospitals is outperforming the management in the public hospitals, in terms of the control manner. The study documented that the private hospitals are better in providing high-quality service than the public hospitals.

Conversely, Tarawneh (2000) argued that there is no relationship between the privatisation percentage and the increase of the company's management efficiency. The study used the return

on investment and the increasing in sales as indicators to show the effects of privatisation on the company's management efficiency. Privatisation led to improving the financial performance of the Jordanian water company (LIMA) and increases its revenue by 26% (Executive Privatisation Commission, 2001). Moreover, Berqadar (2002) documented that privatisation led to improving financial and operational performance in the Cement Company in Jordan, in addition to a distinct improvement in the quality and characteristics of the product, increase the volume of sales and exports and reduce the company's debts.

Furthermore, Ammari (2002) mentioned that privatisation made an improvement in the financial and operational performance of Jordan Telecom, as measured by the increase of profits and improve the level of service, as well, improve the conditions of the employee. The study assured that privatisation also led to reducing the prices of services provided by the company.

Another study discussed the impact of privatisation on the financial situation and the prices of services provided by the Jordanian telecommunications company, the level of technological progress the company has reached, and the Jordanian experience compared with their counterparts from Arab and international experiences.

The study documented that privatisation has positive effects on the financial position and the price of the provided service and that technological development that has occurred due to implement privatisation (Al-Rabadi, 2003). Oqdeh (2009) added that privatisation leads to improving the financial and operating performance, regarding increase the profitability, efficiency, dividend payment and decrease the employee number in the privatised companies. In contrast, Hazaimah (2004) argued that privatisation does not lead to improving the financial and operating performance. His results opposed the prevailing ideas and documented that privatisation negatively affects the financial and operating performance, and the performance results before privatisation are better than after.

Table 1: Jordanian Privatised Companies

Company Name	Privatisation Date	Sector
Jordan New Cable	1997	Industry
Al-Zay Ready Wear Manufacturing	1997	Industry
National Chlorine Industries	1997	Industry
Jordan Sulpho Chemicals	1997	Industry
The Industrial Commercial and Agriculture company	1999	Industry
Jordan Dairy	1999	Industry
Jordan Press Foundation	1999	Service
Jordan Ceramic Industries	1999	Industry
Jordan Worsted Mills	1999	Industry
Jordan Cement Factories	1999	Industry
Jordan Poultry Processing and Marketing	2000	Industry
Arab International Hotel	2000	Tourism
Jordan Tanning	2000	Industry
Jordanian Duty Free Shops	2000	Service
Jordan Telecom Group	2000	Telecommunication
Jordan Petroleum Refinery	2002	Energy & Utility
The Public Mining	2002	Industry
Jordan National Shipping Lines	2002	Transportation
Arab Potash Company	2003	Industry
Jordan Express Tourist Transport	2004	Transportation
The Phosphate Mines	2006	Industry
Jordan Electric Power	2007	Energy & Utility
Irbid District Electricity	2008	Energy & Utility

3. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Literature shows that changing ownership (privatisation) led to improving state-owned companies' performance. Despite the long history of privatisation, most studies were conducted in developed countries, while few studies were conducted in developing countries, particularly in Jordan. This limited evidence of theories and approaches reflects the wide knowledge gap in privatisation programs and its ability to change companies' performance. In Jordan, there is little literature regarding privatisation's effect on companies' performance, and this study could be the first in-depth study of all privatised companies in Jordan since the beginning of the program in 1996.

The government in Jordan faced a high level of criticism according to the poor performance of the state enterprises. There were calls that government should be responsible for reducing borrowing from the Treasury, with a demand to let the private sector take a role in increasing

the GDP. This study assesses the privatisation program for a broad range of decision-makers to evaluate their past and future decisions. It also provides useful data for the government and stakeholders.

This study highlights two options for the government, either to keep playing the dominant role or to switch to the privatisation program to enhance the performance and stop the source drain and allocate it to other projects. On the other hand, the result can affect shareholders' decisions because shareholders always look for the best alternative which gives the highest return on their investment. Furthermore, the study gives managers a tool to assess how much their company performs efficiently and the management can achieve the shareholder's aims. It is also relevant to lender's attention because lenders are always looking for companies with high performance and high ability to cover all financial obligations

The contribution of this study will be useful for both academia and industry. It will provide an idea about assessing privatisation programs in enhancing the performance in Jordanian SOEs, enable the decision-makers to better understand when and how to privatise, and help to expand and strengthen the understanding the theoretical aspects of the privatisation program.

References

- Al-Rabadi, D. (2003), Privatization of Jordanian Telecommunication Sector a Comparatives Study With Some Arab Countries Experiences. Master Thesis. Yarmouk University
- Ammari, SH. (2002), Jordan Telecom Model of Success for Privatization. A Working Paper Submitted To The Workshop. Jordan: New Vision Jordan's Privatization Program.
- B., & Brusco, S. (2003). The Economic Value Added (EVA®): An Analysis Of Market Reaction. *Advances in Accounting*, 20(07071), 265– 290.
- Börjesson, M., & Dalberg, T. (2021). Massification, unification, marketization, internationalization: a socio-political history of higher education in Sweden 1945–2020. *European Journal of Higher Education*, 11(3), 346-364
- Clarke, G. R., Cull, R., & Shirley, M. M. (2005). Bank privatization in developing countries: A summary of lessons and findings. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 29(8-9), 1905-1930.
- Darwazeh, R. N., & Dabaghia, M. (2018). Privatization Effect on Shareholder Value in the Jordanian State Owned Enterprises. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 8(2), 70.
- Giraldo, J. K. (2021). Defense budgets, democratic civilian control, and effective governance. In *Who Guards the Guardians and How* (pp. 178-207). University of Texas Press
- Gokgur, N., & Christen, R. (2009). Impact of restructuring and Privatizing State-owned Infrastructure and Non-infrastructure Enterprises in Jordan, 1994-2008. POHL Consulting and Associates
- Gokgur, N., & Christen, R. (2009). Impact of restructuring and Privatizing State-owned Infrastructure and Non-infrastructure Enterprises in Jordan, 1994-2008. POHL Consulting and Associates.

- Kikeri, S., & Nellis, J. (2004). An assessment of privatization. *The World Bank Research Observer*, 19(1), 87-118.
- Kikeri, S., & Nellis, J. (2004). An assessment of privatization. *The World Bank Research Observer*, 19(1), 87-118.
- Kouser, R., Azid, T., & Ali, K. (2012). Financial and operating performance of privatized firms: A case study of Pakistan. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 87(87), 90-116.
- Maditinos, D. I., Sevic, Z., & Theriou, N. G. (2006). The Introduction of Economic Value Added (EVA ®) In the Corporate World. *The Southeuropean Review of Business and Accounting*, 4(2), 1-11.
- Mansfield, E. D., & Pollins, B. M. (Eds.). (2009). *Economic interdependence and international conflict: New perspectives on an enduring debate*. University of Michigan Press.
- Nahala 2002 Jordan telecom privatization appraisal master thesis manuscript Jordan University
- Oqdeh, L. N., & AbuNassar, M. A. N. (2011). Effects of Privatization on Firms Financial and Operating Performance" Evidence from Jordan. *Dirasat: Administrative Sciences*, 161(717), 1-32.
- Parker, D. (2004). The UK's privatisation experiment: The passage of time permits a sober assessment. Available at SSRN 514224.
- Rahbar, F., Sargolzaei, M., Ahmadi, R., & Ahmadi, M. (2012). Investigating the effects of privatization on the economic growth in developing countries: A fixed effects approach. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 3(4), 61-66.
- Rahbar, F., Sargolzaei, M., Ahmadi, R., & Ahmadi, M. (2013). The Effects of Government's Financial Polices on Economic Growth and Income Distribution (Case Study: Iran). *Growth*, 2(4), 336-342.
- Shirley, M. M., & Walsh, P. P. (2000). *Public versus private ownership* (Vol. 2420). World Bank Publications.
- Seppälä, O. T., Hukka, J. J., & Katko, T. S. (2001). Public-private partnerships in water and sewerage services: Privatization for profit or improvement of service and performance? *Public Works Management & Policy*, 6(1), 42-58.
- Savas, E. S., & Savas, E. S. (2000). *Privatization and public-private partnerships*.
- Warner, M. E., Aldag, A. M., & Kim, Y. (2021). Privatization and intermunicipal cooperation in US local government services: balancing fiscal stress, need and political interests. *Public Management Review*, 23(9), 1359-1376